

Novel in vivo porcine models of chronic ischemic tissue

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ABSTRACT

There is a lack of reliable in vivo models that replicate limb-threatening ischemia in humans. To fill this gap, we developed and validated two novel porcine ischemic models: ischemic limb and dorsal flap models, both with and without streptozotocin-induced hyperglycemia ($N = 3$ per group, 12 in total). Hind limb ischemia model was induced via different arterial ligations, with two ischemic and three control wounds per animal. In the flap model, four full-thickness flaps were created on the dorsum with silicone sheets to block reperfusion, and excisional wounds were made on the top. One non-ischemic wound served as control. Transcutaneous oxygen pressure (TcPO₂), wound area, and microvascular density were measured, with TcPO₂ and wound area assessed longitudinally. Data analysis focused on detailed visualization and Bayesian hierarchical modelling to account for the small sample size. Developed models exhibited stable ischemia and prolonged wound healing, with TcPO₂ remaining under 30 mmHg over 28 days, and wound healing extending beyond two weeks. The flap model showed slower TcPO₂ recovery and greater chronicity compared to the limb model, without reliable effect of hyperglycemia. Thus, the porcine flap model shows the highest potential as a relevant model for chronic limb-threatening ischemia.

1. Introduction

Chronic limb-threatening ischemia (CLTI) poses a severe condition associated with high morbidity, mortality, and frequent limb amputations. A key factor hindering wound healing in ischemic conditions is poor tissue perfusion, often caused by peripheral artery disease (PAD), which restricts oxygen supply and promotes development of chronic wounds (Husakova et al., 2022). Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a major contributor to PAD and a leading cause of CLTI, particularly through the development of diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) (Lindner, 2021); (Takahara, 2021). DFUs carry a higher risk of amputation, highlighting the urgent need for effective strategies to improve tissue oxygenation and wound healing (Husakova et al., 2022).

Therapeutic angiogenesis through gene-, cell-, protein-, and drug-

based approaches, shows promise in improving blood flow and tissue repair in CLTI (Han et al., 2022). However, the development of effective therapies is limited by the lack of reliable preclinical models that accurately mimic the complex ischemic conditions seen in humans, which are essential for evaluating new treatments before clinical trials (Veith et al., 2019).

In this study, we aimed to fill this gap and develop and validate a novel porcine model designed to replicate chronic ischemic tissue conditions in human CLTI. By using two models—dorsal full-thickness ischemic flaps and hind limb ischemia induced by arterial ligation—we aim to establish a versatile and clinically relevant platform for future preclinical research. Diabetes was induced in a subset of animals to better reflect the role of hyperglycemia in ischemic wound healing.

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Fig. 1. Drawing of the triple ligation method. The figure shows a sketch of aortic branching in a pig. The black circles indicate the ligation sites on the right external and both internal iliac arteries (“triple ligation”).

Fig. 2. Intraoperative image of arterial ligation (“triple ligation”). The figure shows ligation of the right external and both internal iliac arteries (“triple ligation”). The red dot indicates the aorta, green the ligated right external iliac artery (EIA), yellow the ligated right internal iliac artery (IIA), orange the ligated left IIA, blue the common trunk of both IIA and purple the left EIA.

Key parameters such as tissue oxygenation, wound healing velocity, and microvascular density are evaluated. The Bayesian modelling is used to estimate how accurately the animal models mimics the chronicity and healing challenges observed in human CLTI and diabetic foot ulcers.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Ethic statement

All methods were carried out in accordance with relevant guidelines and regulations. All experiments were conducted in full compliance with European Union Guidelines for Scientific Experimentation on Animals with the permission of Ethical Committee on Animal Research of the Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine (Prague, Czech Republic) and by the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic and carried out according to the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (Act on the Protection of Animals against Cruelty - Act No 246/1992

Fig. 3. Full thickness flap on the dorsum with silicone sheet on the bottom of the wound. The figure shows insertion of the silicone sheet underneath the ischemic flap to prevent vascular regrowth from the bottom.

Fig. 4. Full thickness ischemic flaps on the dorsum. The figure shows four full thickness ischemic flaps on the dorsum with underlying silicone sheet and four ischemic excisional wounds on the top of each flap. Non-ischemic control excisional wound on the dorsum is located outside ischemic flap area.

Fig. 5. Colour change of the right hind limb. The figure shows colour change of the right hind limb immediately after arterial ligation.

Fig. 6. Time trajectories of TcPO₂ from the day of wound formation (D0) to the final measurement (D28), with colour defining treatment group.

(A) Change of TcPO₂ across individual wounds. Control (grey lines) show TcPO₂ in non-ischemic wounds. (B) Model-based estimates of TcPO₂ over the time. Wide coloured lines show median posterior fit, polygons show 95 % credible intervals. Grey lines show TcPO₂ trajectories across individuals wounds. The estimation was based on Bayesian hierarchical generalized linear model with Gamma likelihood (see methods for details).

Coll., Czech Republic). All experimental protocols and experiments were approved by the Ethical Committee on Animal Research of the Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine (Prague, Czech Republic) and the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic (licence MZDR 40632/2018–4/OVZ - 69/2018).

2.2. ARRIVE statement

This study complies with the ARRIVE (Animal Research: Reporting in Vivo Experiments) guidelines for reporting animal experiments (Percie

du Sert et al., 2020).

2.3. Experimental animal

Twelve female pigs (*sus scrofa f. domestica*) weighing 25–30 kg were used in this study. The preference for using females was due to anatomical differences. Male pigs have larger reproductive structures, such as scrotum and accessory glands, which could hinder surgical access to the pelvic arteries. In contrast, female pigs provide a clearer surgical field. Also, female swine are generally considered hormonally

Table 1

Estimated differences in TcPO₂ between groups at the start (A) and at the end (B) of the experiment, and difference between 1-week fold-change (C, slope). CI_L (lower) and CI_U (upper): bounds of the 95 % credible interval. PD: probability of direction. Estimates are based on a Bayesian hierarchical generalized linear model with a Gamma distribution and a log-link function.

	(A) at the start				(B) at the end				(C) difference in slope			
	Ratio	CI _L	CI _U	PD	Ratio	CI _L	CI _U	PD	Ratio	CI _L	CI _U	PD
Limbs vs Flaps (non-diabetic)	2.96	1.08	8.21	0.982	2.40	0.72	7.39	0.924	0.94	0.68	1.31	0.631
Limbs vs Flaps (diabetic)	0.69	0.25	1.93	0.770	2.79	0.91	8.89	0.964	1.42	1.04	1.92	0.987
Limbs vs Flaps (average effect)	1.44	0.69	2.95	0.847	2.60	1.12	5.70	0.986	1.16	0.93	1.45	0.902
Diabetic vs non-DM (flaps)	3.14	1.22	8.02	0.989	1.10	0.35	2.95	0.574	0.76	0.58	1.01	0.973
Diabetic vs non-DM (limbs)	0.74	0.24	2.22	0.715	1.27	0.37	4.40	0.653	1.15	0.79	1.65	0.774
Diabetic vs non-DM (average effect)	1.52	0.72	3.18	0.875	1.19	0.51	2.59	0.663	0.94	0.75	1.17	0.715

more stable.

Animals were obtained from a private supplier and animal breeder (Prague, Czech Republic), who was also the person responsible for the care of the experimental animals.

Animals were randomly moved to the cages one week prior to the beginning of the study.

They were kept in separate cages with an underfloor heating and provided by food and water ad libitum.

2.4. Creation of diabetic animals

After one week of housing, due to homogenous study population (comparable housing condition, similar weight, same gender) and small sample size, animals ($N = 12$) were randomly divided into two groups using a computer based random order generator. Hyperglycemia was induced in one group ('diabetic' or 'DM' pigs) whereas other six animals were intact ('non-diabetic' or 'non-DM' pigs). To induce hyperglycemia, streptozotocin (150 mg/kg) was applied intravenously via central venous catheter placed in internal jugular vein under general anesthesia. Animals were fasted for 12 h prior to this procedure. Hyperglycaemia was maintained, with most values exceeding the upper detection limit (>33.3 mmol/L). A long-acting modified form of insulin, glargine, was administered subcutaneously from day 2 if blood glucose exceeded 30 mmol/L, as a preventive measure against ketoacidosis. The experiment itself was carried out immediately in non-diabetic animals and 28 days after induction of diabetes in diabetic animals.

2.5. Metabolic monitoring

Pigs were weighed at regular intervals throughout the study, and the observed weight gain over the one-month period corresponded to typical growth rates for animals of this age and breed. To further assess the systemic metabolic status, blood samples were collected on days 0 and 28 following STZ administration. Liver function tests (ALT, AST, GGT, ALP, bilirubin) and renal markers (urea, creatinine) revealed no significant changes on day 28 compared to baseline.

2.6. Anesthesia

Animals were fasted for 24 h prior to the surgical procedure. In the cage, before moving to the operating room (OR), Ketamine (10 mg/kg), Azaperone (4 mg/kg) and Atropine (10 mg/kg) were administered intramuscularly. In the OR, Propofol (2 mg/kg) and Fentanyl (2 µg/kg) were applied intravenously and each subject was intubated endotracheally. Anesthesia was maintained with isoflurane 1.5–2.5 % mixed with O₂ and air and continual intravenous injection of fentanyl (2 µg/kg/hod). Vital signs were continuously recorded. Antibiotics (Amoxicillin Bioveta®, 15 mg/kg) were given as a single intramuscular injection before skin incision. All the following procedures and subsequent measurements were performed under general anesthesia. Post-operatively, pain was suppressed by using a transdermal patch.

2.7. Overall description of experimental approach

During the experiment, especially when measuring transcutaneous oxygen pressure, blinding of the study was not possible, as all surgical procedures were recognizable by the type and location of the wounds. However, the surgeon performing the operations did not know whether the animal had diabetes or not, which ensured blinding on the part of the surgeon. The same applies to the person examining transcutaneous oxygen pressure. The assessment of the wound healing velocity and vessel index was also blinded by another physician who evaluated the photographs and histological images. In this case, the examiner did not know what type of surgery was involved or whether the pig had diabetes.

1. Models of ischemic limbs were created in 3 non-diabetic and 3 diabetic randomly selected animals. Pigs were placed in the supine position. The operating field was disinfected with povidone-iodine and covered with sterile covers. Midline incision was performed and transperitoneal approach was established. Afterwards, three types of arterial ligation methods were utilized. Each animal in the designated group (non-DM/DM) underwent a single ligation procedure. Consequently, they each experienced a distinct form of arterial occlusion.

1. isolated ligation of the right external iliac artery (EIA)
2. ligation of the right EIA + right internal iliac artery (IIA)
3. ligation of the right EIA + ligation of both IIA ("triple ligation") (Fig. 1, Fig. 2)

Skin incision was than sutured with non-absorbable interrupted sutures and covered with sterile gauze. Right after limb ischemia creation a pig was turned into a prone position and small excisional wounds ($n = 5$, 2×2 cm) were created on the ischemic ($n = 2$) and non-ischemic ($n = 2$) limb and dorsum ($n = 1$). Wounds were covered with sterile bandages. Wounds on the left limb and dorsal excisional wounds served as non-ischemic controls.

2. Models of ischemic flaps were created in 3 non-diabetic and 3 diabetic randomly selected animals. Pigs were placed in the prone position. After removing hair from the dorsum, sketches for subsequent flaps creation were drawn on the skin.

The operating field was than disinfected with povidone-iodine and covered with sterile covers. Afterwards, four full thickness flaps (15×5 cm) were created on the dorsum of each pig. Silicone sheet was inserted underneath each flap to eliminate wound contraction and reperfusion of the flap from the underlying tissue (Fig. 3). Flaps were than secured back to their normal skin levels with interrupted non-absorbable sutures and covered with sterile gauze. Right after dorsal skin flaps creation, small excisional wounds ($n = 5$, 2×2 cm) were created on the top of each flap ($n = 4$). Last wound ($n = 1$) was placed on the dorsum outside of the flap area and served as non-ischemic control (Fig. 4). Wounds were covered with sterile transparent waterproof bandages.

Fig. 7. Wound area over the course of the experiment, from the day of wound formation (D0) to the final measurement (D14), with colour defining treatment group. (A) Change of wound area across individual wounds. Control (grey lines) show the wound area in non-ischemic wounds. (B) Model-based estimates of the wound area over the time. Wide coloured lines show median posterior fit, polygons show 95 % credible intervals. Grey lines show change in wound area per individual wound. The estimation was based on Bayesian hierarchical robust model (see methods for details).

2.8. Clinical evaluation and follow up

2.8.1. Measurement of transcutaneous oxygen pressure (TcPO₂)

Severity of ischemia in limbs and flaps was assessed using TcPO₂ on day 0, 14 and 28 post surgery. TcPO₂ was assessed using a Tina TCM4 series transcutaneous monitor (Radiometer, Copenhagen, Denmark), ensuring accurate sensor placement and temperature regulation. Electrodes were applied in close proximity to excisional wounds. In the flap model, four ischemic excisions were located on the dorsum, with one non-ischemic control wound positioned outside the affected region. The

limb model featured two ischemic excisional sites in the right limb, alongside two non-ischemic control wounds in the left limb, plus an additional non-ischemic wound on the dorsum. Once stabilized, measurements were recorded at consistent intervals to maintain reliability, following established reference ranges.

2.8.2. Wound healing velocity

Photographs of the wounds were taken at days 0, 7 and 14 using a digital camera (Sony, Tokyo, Japan). The surface area of the wound was determined by tracking the wound margins and calculating the wound

Table 2

Estimated differences in wound area between groups at the start (A, D0) and at the end (B, D14) of the experiment, and the change in wound area over time, reflecting healing velocity (C, slope). The more negative the slope, the greater the healing velocity. CI_L (lower) and CI_U (upper) represent the bounds of the 95 % credible interval. PD indicates the probability of direction. Estimates are derived from a robust Bayesian hierarchical linear model.

	(A) at the start				(B) at the end				(C) difference in slope			
	Diff	CI_L	CI_U	PD	Diff	CI_L	CI_U	PD	Diff	CI_L	CI_U	PD
Limbs vs Flaps (non-diabetic)	-153	-286	-19	0.988	-153	-288	-12	0.984	1	-86	87	0.505
Limbs vs Flaps (diabetic)	134	-6	269	0.970	74	-67	215	0.856	-29	-116	60	0.745
Limbs vs Flaps (average effect)	-10	-107	83	0.590	-39	-137	57	0.789	-15	-75	47	0.685
Diabetic vs non-DM (flaps)	-1	-115	115	0.512	-139	-255	-20	0.987	-69	-138	-1	0.976
Diabetic vs non-DM (limbs)	283	128	437	1.000	88	-76	242	0.863	-99	-199	3	0.971
Diabetic vs non-DM (average effect)	141	46	237	0.997	-25	-124	71	0.700	-84	-144	-23	0.997

Fig. 8. Data of vessel index in relation to the time of biopsy.

Points are measurements from individual wounds, lines show model-based estimates of vessel index according to time of biopsy. Polygons show 95 % credible intervals. The estimation was based on Bayesian hierarchical linear model Gamma distribution (see methods for details).

area by the use of ImageJ software (NIH, Bethesda, MD). Subsequently, the daily change in wound size was calculated and statistically evaluated.

2.8.3. Histological analysis and microvascular density (“vessel index”)

Wound biopsy was taken on day 7, 14 and 28 post surgery. Biopsies were performed from a different wound on each of the aforementioned days to maintain wound chronicity, which would be compromised by repeated biopsies. Samples were then fixed with 10 % formaldehyde and embedded into paraffin. Anti-CD31 antibodies were used to label the vessels in histological slides. The number of vessels were then counted under microscope.

After a 10 - fold magnification of the microscope objective, four photographic images of the specimen were taken using a special program linked to the microscope (Quick Photo). The number of vessels in all four images was then manually counted under microscope. The result for a given histological sample was the average value of all measurements in the given four images. The evaluation was carried out by inserting a mark (cross) at the places of the vessels and the data were entered in an Excel table. Slides were mixed and selected for evaluation randomly. Each sample was assigned a specific number that corresponded to one of the five groups (non-diabetic flaps, diabetic flaps, non-diabetic limbs, diabetic limbs, controls), wound number, and day of biopsy. However, the meaning of this number was revealed only after the overall calculation was performed in order to avoid subjective

distortion of the results.

2.9. Euthanasia

At the end of the experiments, subjects were euthanized under deep general anesthesia using a lethal dose of potassium chloride.

2.10. Data analysis

We used R software (version 4.3.2) for the entire data analysis (R Core Team, 2023). Detailed documentation of our analysis process is publicly available online at https://filip-tichanek.github.io/wound_pig/.

Due to small sample size we focused on detailed visualization and Bayesian modelling as it does not rely on large-sample approximation as classical (frequentist) statistics (McElreath, 2020) Specifically, we used Bayesian hierarchical models fitted using the brms package in R (Bürkner, 2017), with hierarchical random intercept of individual wound nested within individual pig.

We analysed three outcomes: (i) measurement of transcutaneous oxygen pressure (TcPO₂, mmHg), (ii) wound area (mm²), and (iii) vessel index. Each outcome was modelled with fixed effect of time (weeks), group (defined by presence of diabetes and wound location [limb vs flap]) and their interaction. TcPO₂ and the vessel index were modelled with a Gamma distribution with log link, whereas the wound area was

modelled using robust regression with student t-distribution.

We used weakly-informative Gaussian priors ($\sigma = 2$, or $2 \times$ standard deviations of wound area, for main effects and 1 for interactions). Priors for group and the group:time interaction were centred at null effect, imposing 'sceptical' prior pushing estimated effect toward the null effect. For the effect of time, priors were set to reflect expectation of healing over time (see Supplementary Materials for details).

To report the uncertainty of the effect estimation, we present 95 % credible intervals (CI) and also calculated the Probability of Direction (PD), which may be interpreted as an index (ranging from 0.5 to 1) representing the certainty that the effect goes in a particular direction (Makowski et al., 2019).

3. Results

Both models, the ischemic limb model and the ischemic flap model, were successfully created in all pigs. No animal died during the peri-, intra- and post-operative phase. No serious complications were observed in peri-, intra- or postoperative period. One pig died preoperatively 5 min after streptozotocin (SZT) application due to the circulatory collapse and was replaced by another animal. Lameness and colour change of the ischemic limb (Fig. 5) was observed in all animals immediately after all three types of arterial ligation and both disappeared within 24 h. As the specific ligation procedure does not seem to have marked influence on the outcomes it was not taken into account in the analysis.

3.1. Measurement of TcPO₂

Wounds in flap model maintained low TcPO₂ levels throughout the whole experiment, whereas TcPO₂ was markedly increasing in limbs (Fig. 6). Congruently, TcPO₂ levels in control wounds initially differed from those in ischemic wounds, but limb wounds gradually matched control levels, unlike flap wounds, which remained distinct through day 28 (Fig. 6) particularly in non-diabetic animals.

The results from the Bayesian hierarchical generalized linear model corroborate these findings (Fig. 6B, Table 1, Suppl. Fig. 1, Suppl. Table 1). The model estimated that ischemic wounds in limb model exhibit a 2.6-fold higher TcPO₂ value compared to flap wounds on day 28. Specifically for non-diabetic and diabetic subgroups, the final TcPO₂ values were approximately 2.4-fold and 2.8-fold greater in limb wounds compared to flaps, respectively (Table 1). The model estimates a 98.6 % probability that limb location enhances TcPO₂ levels by day 28. The model found no reliable support that diabetes disrupts TcPO₂ recovery (Table 1).

Wounds in the flap model exhibited a persistently low TcPO₂ throughout the study period, indicating slower healing process and more severe chronicity for this model group.

3.2. Wound healing velocity

Based on the results obtained, prolonged wound healing was observed in both of the ischemic models (over 2 weeks) and control (non-ischemic) wounds (Fig. 7).

When comparing individual models to each other, the non-diabetic ischemic flaps showed the longest time to heal, followed by the non-diabetic ischemic limbs (Fig. 7). Surprisingly, the diabetic models healed faster although this is likely confounded by larger baseline wound area.

The Bayesian model supports this observation that both initial wound area and healing velocity (weekly rate of wound area reduction) differ between diabetic and non-diabetic pigs (Fig. 7B, Table 2, Suppl. Fig. 2). However, as the difference in baseline value may affect rate of change markedly, the results are difficult to interpret.

Our data do not indicate a notable difference in wound area reduction between the limb and flap models, nor a clear effect of induced

hyperglycaemia on wound closure.

3.3. Vessel index

Decrease in vessel count was observed in both of non-diabetic and diabetic models of ischemic flaps. In the case of the limb ischemia group in non-diabetic animals, the number of vessels continuously increased throughout the measurement period. The opposite finding was observed in the group of diabetic animals, where the number of vessels decreased to almost half of the original number on day 28.

Given that the data are not longitudinal (measured once per wound) and initial values vary significantly across groups (Fig. 8), reliability of these results is low. Congruently, the Bayesian model shows a large uncertainty in estimates and does not indicate any reliable difference between groups (Suppl. Table 2, 3).

4. Discussion

We successfully established porcine models of chronic ischemic tissue across all experimental groups. Both non-diabetic and diabetic ischemic flap and limb models demonstrated stable ischemia and prolonged wound healing. TcPO₂ levels remained below 30 mmHg even on day 28, and wound closure exceeded two weeks in all cases. These findings suggest that both models provide a clinically relevant platform for evaluating therapeutic angiogenesis. Notably, the non-diabetic flap model exhibited the lowest TcPO₂ values and the slowest wound healing rate, indicating it may represent the most stringent and suitable model for such investigations. Developing a relevant animal model for CLTI remains challenging due to the complexity of the condition (Sanapalli et al., 2021). Current models often fail to replicate key features like impaired angiogenesis and neuropathy seen in diabetic patients (Mieczkowski et al., 2022). Although porcine models have shown greater similarity to human physiology compared to small-mammal models, rapid collateral vessel formation limits their utility (Sullivan et al., 2001), (Gao et al., 2020). For this reason, we believe that to obtain a suitable ischemic limb model, it is necessary to ligate the source of collaterals. To address this, our "triple ligation" strategy (ligation of the external iliac artery and both internal iliac arteries) successfully created stable ischemia in porcine models, with TcPO₂ remaining <30 mmHg for 28 days and wound healing exceeding two week, implying prolonged wound healing and stable ischemia.

Interestingly, we did not find any evidence that diabetic wounds heal longer than non-diabetic ones. A likely explanation is that diabetic animals had larger wound areas at baseline (day 0), which allowed more room for absolute reduction over time. Since only the initial wound size and slope differed, but not the final wound area, this baseline difference likely accounts for the observed faster closure rate (Fig. 7). This finding may be also limited by the short duration of induced diabetes, which likely excluded long-term complications such as neuropathy and may not have affected wound healing (Mieczkowski et al., 2022). Another explanation may be that insulin supports wound healing process in streptozotocin-induced animals (Mieczkowski et al., 2021). The results of this study indicates that insulin treatment tends to be more efficient in wound healing in diabetic model than metformin, irrespective of the effect of glycaemic normalization. This could happen due the fact, that insulin and metformin trigger different molecular pathways that influence wound healing in different ways.

Although our findings provide novel insight, the lack of similar studies makes their broader interpretation more difficult. There are paucity of studies addressing the healing of ischemic wounds in streptozotocin-induced diabetic pigs. Based on our previous review (Lovasova et al., 2022) only one study (Velander et al., 2008) specifically examined wound regeneration in this model. Authors created full thickness wounds on the dorsum of diabetic and non-diabetic pigs and reported slower re-epithelialization, reduced wound contraction, and impaired healing in diabetic pigs, associated with lower IGF-1 and TGF- β

levels in wound fluid. PDGF expression remained unchanged, suggesting that impaired healing is not solely driven by local hyperglycemia.

Based on vessel index analysis, in the non-diabetic ischemic limb model, we observed a continuous increase in blood vessels over time, suggesting collateral development, whereas in diabetic limbs, vessel numbers tended to decrease, indicating diabetes may suppress collateral formation (Johnson et al., 2020), (Costa and Soares, 2013). This phenomenon was not observed in ischemic flaps, highlighting the differences between these models. In the ischemic flap model ischemia was induced over a broader area (by damaging multiple small vessels rather than occluding a specific artery) and no clear difference in neovascularization was observed between the diabetic and non-diabetic groups. The number of newly formed vessels decreased over time from day 7 to day 28 in both groups (Fig. 8). This finding may be explained by two factors: first, the absence of arterial ligation likely limited the stimulus for collateral formation; and second, the use of a mesh under each flap — designed to prevent vessel ingrowth — may have effectively suppressed neovascularization in both groups. Although this finding is not reliable given small sample size and non-longitudinal nature of the vessel index measurements, it may be an interesting area of future research.

Our study has several limitations. We used only female pigs which ensured the homogeneity of experimental conditions and minimized biological variability, but may limit generalisability. The sample size was small; to mitigate this, we employed Bayesian statistical methods to maximize the interpretability of the results, and we have made all data and code publicly available to encourage further research and synthesis with similar studies. Finally, we did not assess immunohistopathological parameters, which could have provided deeper insight into the cellular and molecular mechanisms of impaired wound healing in diabetic tissue. Future studies incorporating these parameters could help clarify the underlying mechanisms and allow better evaluation of the model's relevance to human diabetic wound healing.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, we developed four novel porcine models of ischemic tissue. All the models presented with stable ischemia over 2 weeks and extended wound healing over 2 weeks. The ischemic flap model demonstrates characteristics of chronic ischemia and represents a valuable framework for investigating long-term tissue dysfunction and potential therapeutic interventions. Further investigation, particularly regarding the role of diabetes in ischemic wound healing, is needed to refine these models and enhance their relevance to human conditions.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Veronika Frelichova: Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Robert Bem:** Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Jaroslav Chlupac:** Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Michal Dubsky:** Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing. **Jitka Husakova:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Andrea Nemcova:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Ludek Voska:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Zuzana Simunkova:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Filip Tichanek:** Visualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Jiri Fronek:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this article.

Appendix A. Data and code

Data and code to this article are available online at https://filip-tichanek.github.io/wound_pig/.

Data availability

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article and its supplementary information.

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